

Resonance Banking System

Money we earn at the end of a month is always applied to a banking system. The fastest money multiplication method is finding the resonance between sentiment wave and technical wave in any stock of either banks or industries. The same resonance money multiplication techniques can also be used while using credit cards. The Resonance Banking System provides an effective resonance equation between all the money flow dynamics in our life using which exact flow velocity and direction can be determined in a complex money flow system. The Resonance Banking System is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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